

Research Article

Eradicating War by Eradicating the Thought and Psychology of War

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Abstract: Since the origin of civilised human life nowhere humans have been made to believe war is useless and an instinctive negative act that is destructive and useless. Humans may have an animal legacy but now humans are the most evolved and matured species on the earth. Humankind has failed to assert human compassion, empathy, understanding and peace to end all animal instinctive behavior that doesn't suit the status of 'human and humanity'. The current international scenario is full of disputes and issues that are leading to war. All the civilians of all the nations including the rulers have to understand the brutality, destruction, and irrelevance of war. There is grave necessity to denounce might, superiority, invasion, and war completely in the conduct of international affairs. Till now we fought wars because we were made to believe it as an effective weapon of gain, survival, justice, and foreign policy. Humans need to come out of this Psychology and understand that whatever inflicts pain, misery, death and devastation to human life is useless, inhuman, ugly, and animalistic. We as humans have the great necessity of eradicating this psychology of war and should spread 'No War Psychology' from now onwards for all ages. The paper attempts to analyse the present scenario of wars in world politics and tries to explore the methods how to inculcate the Psychology of denouncing war in all walks of human life and the entire world.

Keywords: War psychology, democracy, eradication war, irrelevance of war, human life

INTRODUCTION

Popular spiritual thinker Deepak Chopra quotes, "If you are stuck in the metaphor of war, with its winners and losers, revenge, enmities that last for generations, and the macho image of the warrior, you can never end the war even though you want to. There is no clear end to war once you are in a war mentality. Winners in one war become losers the next, and combat runs into a quagmire in which neither side will be able to claim victory, war thinking keeps stubbornly drilling home the same metaphor of war. As history teaches us from World War I to Vietnam and now Afghanistan, wars are at once pointless, relentless, and endless. War heroes on one side are war criminals on the other."¹

¹ Deepak Chopra, 10 Ways to Resolve All Conflicts and End war, Chopra Foundation, <https://choprafoundation.org/consciousness/10-ways-to-resolve-all-conflicts-and-end-war/accessed> on 23-02-2024.

Dimensions of the psychology of war

Throughout history instinctive authoritative, egoist, revengeful leaders have projected war as natural, inevitable just and unavoidable reality, but the time has come to change all the ancient animal instincts breeding the psychology of war. Modern days with sophisticated weapon technology aided by artificial intelligence will have serious implications for human life. There is an urgent need to eradicate the thinking war as still relevant, and inevitable from human psychology. Unlike the natural and climate disasters, war a big existential threat can be eradicated just by eradicating the psychology of believing in the narration of war as solution.

International politics is full of narrations, force, strength and supremacy that can be comprehended and understood by the ever expanding military expenditure of the nations. Nations are not fighting to protect human life, provide all the basic amenities, and to provide a peaceful living to their citizens but they are fighting for ideologies, status and supremacy without any concern for the human life and destruction. Not only has that, nations succeeded in making people believe war as just, right and a way of self defense and it is essential to think, plan and prepare for the war all the time. Though nations speak of international security, peaceful coexistence, pacific settlement of disputes and diplomatic negotiations, they think preparation for the war and security first and peaceful negotiations last. Nations and people have failed to realise the fact that war is a way of mutual destruction.

Psychological Understanding of the War by Nations and Leaders

War is a cruel, insecure, and unnecessary act of the states that are willing to destroy rather than preserve and protect. Big nations that consider themselves prestigious and strong maintain their status and superiority are guiding the course of history and politics. Political systems are not mature enough to navigate disputes. Big nations and their authoritative leaders don't believe in pacific settlement of disputes because without war they cannot assert their supremacy in world politics and they cannot prove their capability and the strength to kill and destroy. Nations that championed the cause of democracy like the United States and the European Union they too believe war is inevitable and for small and petty reasons they start military strikes. We have forgotten democracy is all about protecting the people who elected the government and believing in discussion and public opinion.

Small nations like Ukraine think that compromising in negotiations will affect their independence and prestige. Fighting without having the capability to face big nations facing war, allowing death and devastation preserves their independence and prestige. After two years of war now Ukraine is preparing for peaceful negotiations. No one taught the world that war is just the problem of narrow understanding and the inability to comprehend the situation and it is a situation of lack of empathy towards human life and their civilians. It is just the problem of right understanding.

The majority of the leaders and civilians have doubts about how to protect the sovereignty and integrity of their nations without war. Without a strong defense, weapon, and military system how to preserve territorial integrity is the biggest doubt and insecurity of the nations. Peace, goodwill, right actions, and human values protect the entire world system. The defense system is useful when a mad foolish if ever invades, to defend, to beat them back and to teach them the lesson of humanity. First accepting the principle of peaceful co-existence and not violating it in all situations is the only answer. Defense systems are not for killing and destroying but to defend and to beat back autocratic stupid foolish nations if ever they invade, it is to teach them a lesson of peace but not to kill. Many great thinkers anticipate war cannot be deemed impossible in

world politics because human stupid, self-destructive instinctive behavior cannot be underestimated and this is the major problem that we need to address in the present century.

Ending the war with strong Psychological and spiritual understanding and actions

Strong psychological resilience is needed to understand the war strategies of the nations. War has been conceived as a helpless necessity, compulsory choice to preserve the valour and prestige of a nation from mythological stories to all the times. Humankind has been misled by this psychology of insecurity. Humans fight with animals because it is not possible to negotiate conflicting interests with them but humans can be negotiated and reached out. Humans have failed to understand preparing for war is preparing for mutual destruction that cannot be recreated, and corrected.

All the humans of the world must realize and say we don't want to see heaps of dead bodies and pools of blood, bodies wrapped in white clothes, orphan children begging in streets and ready to become criminals and terrorists for food and survival, hunger deaths, helpless lives in chaos, people fighting to get the food from the aid agencies and completely devastated civilian and human life. Many wars happen in the name of religion without simple common sense that God is all-pervading he doesn't need our protection. Killing life is killing God because he resides in all living beings. In the name of protecting religion and God they are killing both God and humanity. Hamas hideouts in Gaza and huge long tunnels raise the question, what kind of leaders need these kinds of hideouts and shelters? The people who are involved in illegal underworld activities need secret hideouts. Huge waste of resources for a poor nation like Palastine and now Israel is destroying all the secret infrastructure of Hamas along with public property.

Unity and cooperation at regional level

When the crisis and tension cannot be resolved by one round of negotiations; giving a pause to understand and comprehend the things will again provide other chances of negotiations and better choices. If the world is getting more intelligent, educated, reasonable and logical people then humans have many choices of conflict resolution. Before two world wars European nations had always engaged in one or the other kind of war but after the creation of European Union all of them are united, working with many uniform policies, economic policies, trade and currency and political unity has made the European Union one of the best examples for successful regional organization and cooperation. Because they have experienced the evil consequences of war and have chosen unity. This example better helps to understand the might of unity and peace in the international relations. America, Asia, Africa and Middle East need to understand and to strengthen regional cooperation to eradicate regional conflicts.

Theories are theories of speculation not of solution

Most of the theories of international politics provide a theoretical frame work to understand human nature, economic and political ideas, development and progress but have failed to provide a frame work to understand and resolve international conflicts humanely. Liberalism believes in positive human nature and democratic values in governance. Communism glorifies revolution to settle conflicting interests equates peace with the establishment of communist government, Idealists believe that humans can be educated, conflicts and wars and can be resolved but no definite ideas about resolving war. Realists consider conflicts and wars as natural result of the human nature and wars cannot be stopped. Democracies are being handled without proper discussion, public opinion and tolerance. No sound theories to uphold peace and humanity.

Reforming and Reframing International Institutions

There is a grave necessity of framing and reframing our regional and global institutions to mitigate disputes effectively and to control the nations resorting to war. All the nations proclaim their commitment to international peace, security and belief and support to United Nations (UN) in their foreign policy preferences but supersede UN where the negotiations of the multilateral institution can play an effective role. If the nation is decisive on war then sovereignty and independent decisions are ascertained. To eradicate wars two international institutions were established but they were used for other purposes except to alleviate war. All the nations have to recognize the importance of UN as a global multilateral platform with many options for resolving disputes. Nations have to unite to identify the weaknesses of the UN and should believe in reforming and strengthening the role of UN in conflict resolution. If we analyse the working of both League of Nations and United Nations in the initial years of their establishment; it is really impressing that they succeeded in handling many disputes effectively and providing permanent solutions. Authoritative, dictatorial and assertive leaders are weakening the working of international institutions.

Reality of the International Community

It is painful reality that world is witnessing two wars, huge violation of human rights, destruction of civilian life and property; but no nation is prepared to interfere, mediate and to negotiate. Wars are being considered as domestic affair and nations are allowed to exercise their sovereignty violently destroying their own civilian life and property. European nations are supporting Ukraine with weapons and resources but are not interested in negotiating to stop war. This situation clearly proves if nations are not able to solve their disputes for themselves; none will solve for them. Democratic nations are projecting themselves as helpless spectators and weak in solving disputes for them and also for others. Political leaders are very selfish and don't have any genuine concern for the international peace, security and human life. Intellectuals are projecting this as beginning of the third world war, the agony is that, they too think that wars cannot be stopped and entire human world cannot do anything but to accept death, violence and destruction.

Nations and people must adopt a mindset that all are equal and have equal rights to life on earth. Preservation and protection of this right must be the foremost and prominent agenda of nations. Humans need to trust humans. Developing compassion for the whole of humanity and accepting the mindset not to kill and destroy. Humans are capable of revolutionary technological innovations and explorations, is it difficult to understand their revenge, insecurity, anger, and instincts? Is it difficult to practice peace, compassion, respect, and empathy with other humans? We need to end the war in our minds first and then overcome the evil through cooperation and coordination. It is about building trust within us and in our behavior. We must not wait for some savior to come, to build trust between us, and to uphold some universal values for the human community. Everyone has to learn these values and end the war.

There is an urgent necessity of providing basic value education to all whether they are civilians or leaders. How peaceful coexistence can benefit humanity and contribute to the physical and mental well-being of the whole population of the world? When peace and empathy pervade all the thinking and actions of the people and leaders war becomes useless. Are we humans so instinctive and stupid that anybody can disturb our peace and have a disastrous impact on our nations?

Illiteracy, ignorance, backwardness, and religious fundamentalism are a big threat to human life and freedom. When the entire world is analyzing the impact of artificial intelligence on human life, religious fundamentalists are worrying about how to make everyone respect their religion and scriptures. What to eat? How to dress? What to prey? How to prey? How to make everyone comply with the scriptures has become the agenda of the religious groups. They want to show the world the greatness of their religion, they want to conquer and impose their religious laws on everyone to make their God happy. The big challenge is How to make these people educated? And How to make them understand the value of human life? They don't know that they are in contradictory understanding, if you know where your God is then you can protect him, if you say your God is all-pervading omniscient, and omnipotent then he is everywhere and within everyone then protecting all forms of life is the highest form of devotion to God.

Not only enlightening people and leaders are necessary to better the situation; also a strong humane international organization capable enough to command respect and capable enough to navigate disputes between the nations is the need of the hour. All the nations should foster respect and commitment to such institutions and should support them for pacific settlement of disputes. Spiritual thinker and writer Deepak Chopra provides a few ideas to understand the psychology of war before handling it. He suggests regarding de-escalating the concept of the enemy, treating the opposite side with respect, recognizing the different perceptions, forgiving, refraining from belligerence, using emotional intelligence, understanding the other side's values and ideas completely, recognizing the fear within, not insisting on their right perception to navigate disputes effectively as these reforms work wonders in all types of negotiations.²

As famous writer Yuval Noah Harari Quotes Humans were able to survive and control the universe because of their power to cooperate and coordinate better than other animals. He describes that the peaceful termination of the Cold War proves that if humans make the right decision, even superpower conflicts can be resolved peacefully.³ Nations with self-pride and extreme nationalism should not forget the fact that war is devastating in the 21st century and here no gainers both winners and losers are the losers.

If all the nations can think maturely in politics wars can be eliminated. When war is denounced by the majority of the nations, all the nations can best use their resources focusing on their all round development. Democracies with a strong will can alleviate the root cause of war. Famous philosopher J. Krishna Murthy says where there is a cause; the effect can be ended because the cause can be ended.⁴ This ending will improve the overall inner and outer well-being of humans and nations. Power, dictatorship, and authoritarian leaders led the world to wars in the past century. We have to make the 21st century an era of spirituality where realizing the highest divinity in humans should be the main quest. Spiritual quest and understanding inculcate peace, compassion, understanding, and integrity within the deep inner self of humans that leads to peaceful, tolerant, and humanitarian behavior in individuals. We all belong to the same civilization on this earth, to live peacefully without destruction we need to stop thinking of war as an option of foreign policy mentally first. Preserving life should be the main agenda of sovereign nations. Enlightened statesmanship that believes in only peace, not in power is the need of the modern times because peace is not a utopia to be realized, it is a positive and human reality to be lived.

² Deepak Chopra, 10 Ways to Resolve All Conflicts and End war, Chopra Foundation, <https://choprafoundation.org/consciousness/10-ways-to-resolve-all-conflicts-and-end-war/>

³ Yuval Noah Harari, 21 Lessons for the 21st Century, Penguin Publications, 2019, United Kingdom, pp200-212.

⁴ <https://www.krishnamurti.in/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/War-20-3-22.pdf>, accessed on 23-2-2024

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